

QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Think about your last professional learning experience (course, lecture, event, boot-camp, etc.) that was, in some way, sponsored or supported by your company. This sponsorship may have been:

Financial: Full or partial payment of the registration/tuition fee.

Time: Full or partial release from your working hours to participate.

Considering your last experience with these characteristics, was it Mandatory or Optional?

- **Mandatory:** I participated because it was a formal requirement from the company for my current role, to meet regulations, or essential strategies.
- **Optional:** I participated by my own choice, taking advantage of a benefit or support offered by the company (financial or time), for my professional development.

Sociodemographic and Professional Profile

This section will collect data for sample segmentation and comparative analyses.

2. **What is your age?** _____
3. **Which gender do you identify with?**
 - Female
 - Male
 - Non-binary
 - Prefer not to answer
 - Other: _____
4. **In which State do you reside?** _____
5. **What is your highest level of education?**
 - Incomplete High School
 - Complete High School
 - Incomplete Higher Education
 - Complete Higher Education
 - Incomplete Postgraduate (Specialization, Master's, or PhD)
 - Complete Postgraduate (Specialization, Master's, or PhD)
6. **What is your total experience time in software engineering?**
 - Up to one year.
 - Between 1 and 2 years.
 - Between 3 and 4 years.
 - Between 5 and 6 years.
 - Between 7 and 8 years.
 - More than 8 years.
 - Prefer not to answer

7. Which of the alternatives below describes your current professional level?

- Student / Intern / Trainee
- Junior
- Mid-level (Pleno)
- Senior
- Specialist / Principal (Focus on individual technical contribution)
- Lead / Coordinator / Manager (Focus on people management)
- Prefer not to answer
- Other: _____

8. How many employees does the company have?

- Up to 9 employees (Micro enterprise)
- From 10 to 49 employees (Small enterprise)
- From 50 to 99 employees (Medium enterprise)
- 100 or more employees (Large enterprise)
- Prefer not to answer

9. What is your main area of activity in software engineering at the moment?

- Development
- Architecture
- DevOps
- Design (UI/UX)
- Technical Leadership
- People / Project Management
- Data Science
- Quality Assurance (QA)
- Other: _____

Characterization of the Most Recent Learning Experience

This part of the questionnaire will identify the characteristics of the professional learning experience evaluated.

10. **Rate the following statements:**

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I understood how the learning experience connected with the company's goals.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I had the necessary support and resources (time, technology, support) from the company to undertake this learning experience.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I knew who in my company was responsible for organizing the learning experience.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The content of the learning experience met the needs of my role.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The learning experience contained a relevant part dedicated to the development of soft skills (behavioral skills).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My opinion was considered in the creation of the learning experience I participated in.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The content of the learning experience was adapted to my experience level.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

11. Rate the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I participated in this learning experience more out of obligation than interest in the content.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The learning experience was important to keep me competitive in the market.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The leadership in my area actively encouraged my participation in the learning experience.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The company offered clear incentives for participation (e.g., bonuses, time off, etc.).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I had enough time during working hours to participate in the learning experience and study.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The company usually recognizes employees who develop themselves and complete training.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

12. Rate the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
The learning experience I participated in was well organized and structured.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The materials I received for the learning experience were useful.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The environment of the experience (physical or virtual) was suitable for learning.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The instructor's explanation was clear and easy to understand.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The instructor's performance was fundamental to my learning and motivation.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The activities during the experience were interesting and varied.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

13. Rate the following statements:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree
I was satisfied with the quality of the learning experience I participated in.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The learning experience helped me develop my reasoning to solve problems.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What I learned motivated me to seek new knowledge.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The workload of this experience negatively impacted my personal time (rest, social life).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I can apply what I learned in my work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Applying what I learned improved my performance.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
What I learned gave me more autonomy at work.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The support from my leadership was an incentive for me to apply what I learned.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
The experience I undertook opened up growth opportunities within the company.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

About Professional Learning Experiences Throughout Your Career

An analysis of professional learning experiences undertaken throughout your journey in Software Engineering.

14. **What was the most useful learning experience you have ever had at the company? Why?** _____

15. **If you could suggest an improvement in the company's learning processes, what would it be?** _____
